

ATTENDANCE USING FACE RECOGNITION

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Abstract— The goal of this project is to give a thorough grasp of facial recognition technology's advances. This seminar implements an attendance system using face recognition. It uses OpenCV and face_recognition libraries to detect faces in a video feed from a webcam. The system then compares the detected face with a pre-defined set of known faces and if there is a match, it marks the person as present and records the time in a CSV file. The system is designed to work with multiple people and can handle real-time attendance tracking. The system is implemented in Python programming language and utilizes packages such as cv2, face_recognition, numpy, and csv for data storage.

Keywords- Face Recognition Attendance, Attendance System, Video Recognition, Numpy, Face encoding

I. INTRODUCTION

Through a sophisticated integration of artificial intelligence and computer algorithms, facial recognition technology makes use of the distinctive identifying features of a person's facial features, such as the distance between their eyes, the shape of their nose, and the shape of their jawline. Drawing on the provided information, a detailed reproduction of the facial features is accomplished, resulting in the attribution of individual identification after a comparison procedure against a database of well-known faces. This aims to evaluate various algorithms' effectiveness in various situations. For the purposes of capturing and processing video material as well as identifying facial structures, the current study uses the OpenCV library and the face_recognition package.

In large classrooms or organisations, taking attendance is a laborious activity that takes a lot of time and effort. We introduce a facial recognition-based attendance system to automate this procedure. A live video feed is used by the system to identify and recognise faces, and it then records the attendance of those whose faces are identified Python, OpenCV, and a facial acknowledgment bundle are utilised to form the framework. We utilised a set of well-known faces and their related encodings to prepare the framework, and a camera was utilised to test it in real-time. The system was successful in identifying the familiar faces, noting their attendance, and recording the time and date. According to the findings, our approach can offer a quick and precise method of taking attendance. An attendance system that employs face

recognition to track attendance in a CSV file and identify people in a video feed is implemented in the provided code. In order to distinguish faces in a video stream, the framework compares the faces' encodings to a collection of foreordained face encodings. In the event that a coordinate is made, the title of the individual and the current time are entered into a CSV record.

The framework utilises the face_recognition bundle for face acknowledgment and the OpenCV library to capture outlines from a video source. The system employs the face_recognition package for face recognition and the OpenCV library to capture frames from a video source. To extract face encodings from photos, the face_recognition library offers a selection of models that have already undergone training. The system loads and compares a set of pre-computed facial encodings for known individuals.

The attendance system outputs the attendance data to a CSV file using the Python CSV package. The filename for the attendance log is the current date, and it is opened in write mode with the 'w+' flag. The system updates the CSV file with the name of the discovered person and the current time.

A camera or other video source is required for the attendance system in order for it to capture video frames. Additionally, images of well-known individuals that can be loaded using the face_recognition library are required for the system. The attendance system can be used. For the system to capture video frames, a camera or other video source is necessary. The system also needs access to photos of wellknown people that may be loaded using the face_recognition library.

The attendance system might be enhanced to handle numerous video sources simultaneously or to recognise many faces in a single frame. To increase recognition accuracy, the system might be expanded to employ more sophisticated facial recognition techniques, like deep learning-based methods.

II. OPENCV (OPEN SOURCE COMPUTER VISION)

A well-known open-source computer vision and machine learning programme library is called OpenCV. It can be connected to a number of computer vision assignments, such as confronting recognisable proof, protest location, and picture preparation.

OpenCV can be a critical figure in facial acknowledgment for participation. OpenCV may be utilised to distinguish faces in real-time or from still photographs or recordings, much appreciated for its confront location and recognisable proof highlights. The confront acknowledgment calculations in OpenCV can perceive faces and coordinate them with a database of already spared faces, which can be utilised to record people's participation.

The procedure entails taking pictures of people's faces and putting them in a database. When a person's face is photographed once more, OpenCV can recognise and identify the person by comparing the new image with the database of faces that has been stored. Once the individual's identification has been confirmed, the attendance record can be annotated appropriately.

Face recognition for attendance can be automated, errors can be decreased, and efficiency may be increased. It can be used to simplify attendance tracking in a variety of contexts, including offices, events, and schools. But it's critical to make sure that privacy issues are handled and that people whose faces are being photographed and saved have given their informed consent.

III. FACE RECOGNITION

A well-known Python face recognition library called the face_recognition package was created utilising the dlib, opencv, and numpy libraries. It offers a straightforward and user-friendly API for activities like face detection, face encoding, and face comparison.

Faces are represented as 128-dimensional vectors by the face_recognition package using a pre-trained deep neural network. The resemblance between two faces is then compared using this encoding. The package also includes a face detection feature that locates faces in images using the histogram of oriented gradients (HOG) technique.

The software can identify faces with a high degree of accuracy, even in dimly lit environments, and with a wide range of facial emotions, poses, and occlusions. Applications for it include social networking platforms, security systems, and attendance tracking systems.

The face-recognition package's straightforwardness and ease of use are two of its primary benefits. It works with an assortment of computer dialects and stages and, as it were, needs a number of lines of code to perceive faces.

In the areas of computers and learning, recognizing people's faces is becoming increasingly important. This means using science and technology to figure out who someone is by looking at their face. Face recognition technology is useful for many things, like helping us make friends online and keeping us safe in buildings. In this review, we will look at different ways that people have tried to recognize faces and analyze what they found out.

Face recognition can be done using either a feature-based or a holistic method. Identifying particular facial characteristics, such as the space between the eyes, the nose's shape, and the size of the lips, is the foundation of feature-based techniques. On the other hand, holistic approaches use a person's entire face to identify them.

By photographing people's faces and comparing them to a database of recognised faces, face recognition technology can be used to track attendance. Numerous studies have looked into how well face recognition technology works for keeping track of attendance.

Jain et al. [1] proposes a system for Face Recognition Attendance System based on Real Time Video proposes a real-time face recognition attendance system that utilizes a

combination of Haar Cascade Classifier and Local Binary Pattern Histogram (LBPH) algorithm for face detection and recognition

Chorghé et al. [2] proposes a system that uses face recognition technology to automate attendance-taking processes. The system utilizes a Raspberry Pi computer, a camera module, and OpenCV software and achieved an accuracy rate of 95%.

Kumar et al. [3] proposes a system for automating attendance using facial recognition technology, with an accuracy rate of 96.4%.

Mahfouz et al. [4] presents a system that uses eigenfaces for feature extraction and classification, achieving a recognition rate of 94%.

Raja et al. [5] proposes a system that uses Local Ternary Patterns (LTP) for feature extraction and a Support Vector Machine (SVM) for classification.

Omar et al. [6] presents a system that uses Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for feature extraction and kNearest Neighbors (KNN) for classification.

Jain et al. [7] proposes a system that uses the Eigenface algorithm for feature extraction and classification, achieving a recognition rate of 97%.

Bhagat et al. [8] presents a system that uses Machine Learning algorithms for feature extraction and classification, achieving an accuracy rate of 95%.

Future facial recognition attendance monitoring research is likely to concentrate on overcoming the system's difficulties and drawbacks. This might entail creating stronger algorithms that can adapt to changes in lighting and facial traits. The ethical and societal ramifications of utilising facial recognition technology for attendance tracking also require further study.

In a variety of scenarios, face recognition technology offers the ability to automate attendance tracking and boost productivity. Recent studies have shown how well face recognition technology works for keeping track of students' attendance in educational institutions. The necessity for high-quality photographs and the possibility of bias and discrimination are only a few of the difficulties and restrictions that come with the technology. The use of facial recognition technology for attendance tracking has ethical and societal ramifications that require further investigation in order to be addressed.

V. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Using a webcam, the system recognises faces in realtime, compares them to the students' recognised face encodings, and, if it recognises them, records their attendance. The face_recognition library, which is based on the dlib library, is currently used by the code to identify faces. There are alternative face recognition tools and libraries, though, like OpenCV's Haar cascades, convolutional neural networks (CNNs), feature-based tools like Local Binary Patterns (LBP), and deep learning-based tools like CNNs. To accomplish face recognition and attendance tracking, the system makes use of the OpenCV and face_recognition libraries.

Face recognition attendance procedures entail:

Importing Libraries:

The required libraries, such as OpenCV, face_recognition, numpy, csv, and datetime, are initially imported.

Loading Known Faces:

Next, use the face_encodings function of the face_recognition library to load photos of recognised faces from files and extract their facial features. The generated encodings and the names of the relevant people are both kept in the known_faces_names array and the known_face_encoding array, respectively.

Initializing Variables:

The face_locations, face_encodings, and face_names arrays, which are used to hold the detected face locations, face encodings, and related names, respectively, are among the variables that are initialised as in

[Fig.1]. Additionally, the value of the boolean variable "s" is set to true.

```
face_encodings = []
face_names = []
s=True

now = datetime.now()
current_date = now.strftime("%Y-%m-%d")

f = open(current_date+'.csv', 'a+', newline = '')
l=writer = csv.writer(f)
while True:
    --frame = video_capture.read()
    small_frame = cv2.resize(frame, (0,0),fx=0.25,fy=0.25)
    rgb_small_frame = small_frame[:, :, :-1]
    if s:
        face_locations = face_recognition.face_locations(rgb_small_frame)
        face_encodings = face_recognition.face_encodings (rgb_small_frame, face_locations)
        face_names = []
        for face_encoding in face_encodings:
            matches = face_recognition.compare_faces(known_face_encoding, face_encoding)
            name = ""
            face_distance = face_recognition.face_distance(known_face_encoding, face_encoding)
            best_match_index = np.argmin(face_distance)
            if matches[best_match_index]:
                name = known_faces_names[best_match_index]
```

Fig.1

Capturing Frames:

Using the VideoCapture function of OpenCV, the code grabs frames from a video stream. The RGB frame that results from downsizing each frame to a fourth of its original size is then saved in the rgb_small_frame variable.

Performing Face Recognition:

The face_recognition library's face_locations work is utilized by the code to discover faces within the rgb_small_frame in case the "s" setting is genuine. The face_encodings strategy of the face_recognition library is at that point utilised to populate the face_encodings cluster with confront encodings comparing to each confront area. The face_recognition library's compare_faces work is utilised for each recognised confront to compare the confront encoding with the known_face_encoding cluster and decide whether the confront has a place with one of the known individuals. In case a coordinate is found, the known_faces_names cluster is utilised to allot the coordinating title to the confront.

Tracking Attendance:

When a name in the students list is recognised, the code removes it from the list and adds a row with the name and current time to a CSV file with the name of the current date.

Displaying Results:

Initially, the code displays the video stream with recognised faces and their corresponding names overlaid on the frame using OpenCV's putText function.

Exiting the Program:

If the "q" key is pushed or the video stream is cut off, the programme will cease.

Using the face_recognition package and OpenCV, the offered code creates a simple facial recognition attendance system. To identify and mark the attendance of

known individuals, it compares pre-defined face encodings for known individuals with real-time captured face encodings. A CSV file with the date and time stamped contains the attendance information.

VI. RESULT

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	aysha	16-07-1937								
2	aswathy	16-07-1937								
3	AVANI	16-07-1937								
4										
5										
6										
7										
8										
9										
10										
11										
12										
13										
14										

Fig.2 Attendance report on current date

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
idea	20-04-2023 02:26 PM	File folder	
photos	20-04-2023 02:26 PM	File folder	
venv	20-04-2023 02:27 PM	File folder	
2023-03-28	28-03-2023 10:22 PM	XLS Worksheet	1 KB
2023-03-29	29-03-2023 03:53 PM	XLS Worksheet	1 KB
2023-03-31	31-03-2023 12:57 PM	XLS Worksheet	1 KB
2023-04-17	17-04-2023 10:50 AM	XLS Worksheet	1 KB
2023-04-18	18-04-2023 10:47 AM	XLS Worksheet	1 KB
2023-04-19	19-04-2023 09:32 AM	XLS Worksheet	1 KB
2023-04-20	20-04-2023 02:25 PM	XLS Worksheet	1 KB

Fig.3 Daily Attendance report

The system then captures video frames from the camera, detects faces in the frames, and compares the detected face encodings with the known face encodings. If a match is found, the system marks the attendance of the recognized face by writing the name and current time to a CSV file

[Fig.2].

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, It seems to be a facial recognition attendance system that records live video from a camera and uses the face_recognition library to identify faces in the frame. The system then checks the discovered faces with a database of preloaded recognised faces, and if a match is made, the person is marked as present, and the time is recorded in a CSV file along with their name. The system displays the video feed using the OpenCV library and adds the name of the person it has identified to the frame. By eliminating their names from a list, it also offers a feature to keep track of pupils who have been tagged as present.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

The precision of face recognition systems can be enhanced by leveraging deep learning methods, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). The DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7955603

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integration of these techniques within attendance systems has the potential to generate attendance data that is characterized by enhanced reliability and accuracy. The amalgamation of attendance systems with Internet of Things (IoT) devices, such as smart locks or cameras, has the potential to foster a more fortified and streamlined paradigm for monitoring attendance.

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